

Bounding Byzantine Impact in Open CRDT Systems

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Abstract

Conflict-free Replicated Data Types (CRDTs) enable highly available and eventually consistent data replication without coordination, making them well suited for open and partition-prone environments. Recent work has shown that CRDTs can be extended to tolerate Byzantine faults by ensuring that replicas eventually agree on the validity of operations, even in permissionless settings. However, validity alone does not prevent a Byzantine participant from inflicting unbounded damage by issuing large volumes of adversarial yet well-formed updates. For example, when editing text, an attacker can easily delete all prior text. In this paper, we study how to bound the impact of Byzantine behavior in open CRDT systems. We introduce bounded Byzantine CRDTs, a rate-limiting framework for CRDTs in which each update carries an associated cost that limits the influence of adversarial operations relative to the resources they expend. Overall, this work bridges the gap between Byzantine-tolerant CRDTs and resource-bounded adversarial models, providing a principled foundation for deploying CRDTs in fully open, adversarial environments.

1 Introduction

Transient partitions in a distributed system can be seen as benign, non-Byzantine failures that affect availability but not safety, as messages are delayed rather than corrupted or forged. Still, partitions have an impact on system design as they force a choice between preserving data consistency versus favouring availability [10]. Favouring availability implies accepting some level of data divergence. Conflict-free Replicated Data Types (CRDTs) [22] allow divergence and ensure that, when communication occurs, data eventually converges in a deterministic way. However, the standard model of CRDTs assumes a system model where replicas are correct and only subject to non-adversarial failures such as crashes, message loss, reordering, or network partitions.

More recently, a design for Byzantine fault-tolerant CRDTs [14] shows that CRDTs can tolerate Byzantine behavior even

in open, permissionless environments, without requiring costly consensus algorithms. Based on cryptographic hashes of operations, such a design ensures that correct nodes eventually agree on whether an update is valid or not. In fact, under this model, any state update issued by a Byzantine node can only be accepted if it is indistinguishable from one coming from a correct node. However, even when operations are syntactically well-formed and accepted by correct nodes, a Byzantine attacker can still cause substantial harm.

A common use case for CRDTs is editable sequences, which enable shared text documents, as implemented in systems such as Automerge [11] and, as widely reported, in the iOS/macOS Notes app¹. In this setting, a Byzantine node may disrupt the system by overwriting or invalidating large portions of prior work. This behavior is common in Wikipedia edit wars (back-and-forth series of reverts between editors), and it is mitigated by a combination of social processes, moderation policies, and rate-limiting mechanisms rather than purely technical enforcement.

Another well-known example of an open, permissionless environment is the Bitcoin network and its most popular digital currency, BTC. The network protocol and its Byzantine fault-tolerant consensus mechanism ensure double-spending protection through consensus by carefully tracking the creation of coins (unspent transaction outputs) and their transfers between participants. While a Byzantine attacker cannot create new coins out of thin air, it can transfer small fractions of owned coins to multiple destination addresses, effectively spamming recipients. In the case of Bitcoin, the monetary value of BTC makes this behavior largely benign, as it incurs fees and recipients accrue value. In other permissionless systems, however, similar spam patterns can be problematic: for example, for speculative tokens (such as meme coins), such transfers constitute genuine spam, cluttering recipients' wallets with low- or zero-value assets, and such transactions can also bloat the blockchain state, increasing storage requirements for all nodes regardless of wallet-level filtering.

¹<https://github.com/dunhamsteve/notesutils/blob/master/notes.md>

Figure 1. A totally ordered log representing a sequence of set operations, with final set state $\{y\}$ since x was removed.

More generally, most permissionless systems are vulnerable to so-called Sybil attacks, where an attacker creates multiple identities to disrupt system operation. In these scenarios, such behavior would be considered correct by traditional Byzantine-tolerance algorithms. This calls for complementing Byzantine tolerance with rate-limiting mechanisms.

To this end, we propose a resource-bounded adversary model, orthogonal to Byzantine fault tolerance. We assume existing mechanisms ensure validity and convergence, and instead focus on bounding the rate and cumulative impact of valid operations.

Our mechanism leverages a modified version of proof of work (PoW), in which the required computational effort is proportional to the impact of the associated CRDT operations, rather than to the raw operation count. This allows higher-impact operations to incur proportionally higher effort, thereby limiting the rate and consequences of adversarial behavior without sacrificing availability.

In this paper, we begin by describing the guarantees already achievable by systems that support CRDT liveness and convergence in Byzantine settings [14], and then analyze approaches to bounding Byzantine behavior in terms of the impact of individual operations. We offer examples of how our approach can be used and tailored to specific applications. We also discuss alternative mechanisms that could avoid PoW, e.g., the use of predicates that accept new operations based on evidence that they contribute beneficially to the system.

2 Byzantine CRDTs

To understand how Byzantine CRDTs are constructed, we first review the properties of totally ordered logs and how they can be maintained in Byzantine settings. We then extend this discussion to partially ordered logs, which can accommodate partition tolerance.

2.1 Totally ordered logs

The value of a sequential data type is determined by its initial state and a totally ordered sequence of operations, see Figure 1. In a centralized system, this sequence can be represented by maintaining an append-only log. To prevent modifications to past operations, each log entry can include a cryptographic hash of the previous entry, thereby forming a hash-chained log. If the log is made public and replicated by multiple parties, any alteration of historical entries becomes detectable, as it would produce hashes different from those already observed and stored by other participants.

Figure 2. A partially ordered log where a total order up to $\text{add}(y)$ is followed by two concurrent sequences of operations. The final set state under add-wins semantics would be $\{y, z\}$, since $\text{add}(y)$ wins over concurrent $\text{rmv}(y)$.

Creating hash-chained logs and publishing them from a single location (namely, the operation issuer) ensures consistency, but not availability, as a single source of truth prevents conflicting versions even during network partitions. When multiple nodes are allowed to issue operations, two design options arise. (a) If the membership of issuing nodes is known, a consensus protocol [5, 16] can be used to agree on the next operation to append to the log. (b) If the system is open and potential issuers are unknown, Sybil-resistant consensus such as those using proof-of-work [7] can be used to probabilistically converge on the log that has been extended the furthest [18]. In the former case, network partitions primarily degrade liveness and availability, whereas in the latter, they primarily weaken finality.

A totally ordered log is a powerful construct that can support system-wide invariants such as the absence of double-spending, but it is inherently sensitive to network partitions. In contrast, highly available, partition-tolerant data types such as CRDTs can be expressed by relaxing the total-order requirement, which leads us to consider partially ordered logs.

2.2 Partially ordered logs

On any node in a distributed system, the value of a CRDT can be determined by observing the partially ordered log (PO-log) known to that node [3]; see Figure 2. Nodes are free to append their own operations to the PO-log, propagate it to other nodes, and merge incoming PO-logs into their local PO-log. All these actions are partition-tolerant.

This construction can be made more robust by creating hash-chained PO-logs, a concept described as Merkle-DAGs in [21] and further developed in [14]. Updates are identified and chained in the PO-log by computing a cryptographic hash of each *update*, for example using SHA-256. An *update* includes the operation name, its parameters, and the lexicographically ordered list of predecessor hashes, if any.

However, in the above construction, unless node identifiers are included in the update, there is a potential for hash collisions when two nodes independently issue identical operations over identical PO-logs. This ambiguity can be avoided by incorporating a unique replica identifier or a cryptographically strong nonce into the update, ensuring that

each operation is uniquely identified even under concurrent, identical behavior.

In our design, we will assume that nodes possess public-private key pairs. The public key is considered to be the node's ID. Hence, it is included in the update, and the hash of the update block is digitally signed using the corresponding private key. This establishes update authenticity, non-repudiation, and uniqueness. See an example in Figure 3.

We can further define the expected behavior of correct nodes in this setting.

- Correct nodes only extend and propagate PO-logs that are valid with respect to hash-chain integrity, digital signatures, and causal consistency.
- Correct nodes always include, as predecessors, the identities of the locally known maximal elements of the partial order when issuing new updates. This also ensures that each node sequentially extends its most recent operation.

Again, all these procedures are partition-tolerant. We now observe which Byzantine behaviors can (or cannot) be detected.

Detectable Byzantine Behavior. Given hash-chained PO-logs, digitally signed updates, and explicit causal dependencies, several classes of Byzantine behavior can be detected by correct nodes through local verification. In particular, correct nodes can identify any update or PO-log fragment that violates structural or cryptographic validity. First, forgery and impersonation attacks are detectable. Since each update includes the issuer's public key and is signed using the corresponding private key, correct nodes can verify the authenticity of updates and detect any attempt to forge or tamper with operations. Second, attempts to rewrite history are detectable. The use of hash chaining ensures that any modification, removal, or reordering of past updates invalidates the hashes of all dependent updates, making such tampering evident to any node validating the PO-log. Third, causal inconsistencies can be detected. Each update explicitly references the hashes of its causal predecessors, allowing correct nodes to verify that all dependencies are present and that the partial order respects the happens-before relation. Updates that omit required predecessors or introduce impossible causal relations can therefore be rejected. Finally, the propagation of malformed or invalid PO-logs is detectable at merge time. Correct nodes validate hash-chain integrity, signatures, and causal consistency before extending or disseminating PO-logs, preventing the acceptance of structurally invalid histories.

Undetectable Byzantine Behavior. Despite the above guarantees, certain classes of Byzantine behavior remain

undetectable within this model, as they do not violate cryptographic or structural correctness. Most notably, Byzantine nodes may issue operations that are syntactically valid, causally consistent, and correctly signed, yet semantically harmful. Examples include deleting or overwriting large portions of shared state, repeatedly reverting prior work, or otherwise exploiting application semantics to cause damage. Such behavior cannot be distinguished from legitimate operations at the CRDT layer.

Additionally, the model does not prevent or detect excessive operation issuance. A Byzantine node may generate an unbounded number of valid updates, leading to resource exhaustion or disproportionate impact on the shared state. While these operations are individually valid, their cumulative impact may be undesirable. Finally, the use of public-private key pairs does not prevent Sybil behavior. An adversary may generate multiple identities and issue valid updates under each, thereby amplifying its impact without violating any protocol rules.

These limitations highlight that while cryptographic mechanisms enable strong detection of invalid or inconsistent behavior, they do not limit the rate or impact of valid but adversarial operations. Addressing this gap requires mechanisms that impose resource constraints or otherwise limit the potential damage of Byzantine participants.

3 Bounded Byzantine CRDTs

To motivate the need for bounding Byzantine behavior in CRDTs, we consider a simple counter CRDT that supports increment operations of the form $\text{inc}(n)$. In a benign setting, correct nodes typically issue small increments reflecting local events or user actions (e.g., counting the number of detected events at multiple monitoring stations). However, in the presence of Byzantine participants, this assumption no longer holds. A Byzantine node may issue an update such as $\text{inc}(10\,000)$, causing a disproportionate and immediate impact on the replicated state. While such behavior is syntactically valid and causally consistent, it violates the intended application semantics and overwhelms the contributions of correct nodes.

One possible mitigation is to restrict the maximum increment size, for example, by allowing only $\text{inc}(1)$ operations. However, this approach is insufficient in open systems. An adversary may instead generate a large number of Sybil identities, each issuing a single $\text{inc}(1)$ operation. The cumulative effect is equivalent to a single large increment, while remaining fully compliant with syntactic and semantic constraints.

This example illustrates a limitation of CRDTs in open, adversarial environments: bounding the impact of individual operations is insufficient without also bounding the rate or total impact of participating replicas. In the next section, we show how introducing a computational cost per operation

Figure 3. A simple hash-chained partially ordered log. Each update block includes the operation, the issuer public key (ID), the lexicographically ordered list of predecessor hashes, the hash over the previous fields, and a digital signature of that hash.

can address this limitation by constraining the aggregate impact of Byzantine participants.

3.1 Proof-of-Work

A proof-of-work mechanism can be attached to CRDT instances operating in open, adversarial environments to limit the rate and cumulative impact of valid operations.

We consider two functions: a *cost function* $C(\cdot)$ and a *work function* $W(\cdot)$. The cost function

$$C(op, pk, polog) = s$$

deterministically computes a target work amount s for a given operation op and identity pk , optionally taking into account the local PO-log $polog$. This function is data-type dependent and encodes application-specific notions of proportional contribution.

The work function $W(d \cdot s, h)$ produces a proof that an amount of computational effort proportional to s has been expended under a difficulty parameter d , where

$$h = H(op, pk, pred)$$

is the hash of the update to be appended, and

$$pred = \langle H_1, \dots, H_k \rangle_{lex}$$

is the lexicographically ordered list of predecessor hashes. The difficulty parameter d is locally computed, converges system-wide, and regulates the overall cost of work, $cost = d \cdot s$; for now, let us consider $d = 1$; we will discuss adaptive difficulty adjustment in Section 3.1.3.

Concretely, W may be instantiated by searching for a nonce such that the hash of the nonce appended to h satisfies a difficulty predicate (e.g., a required number of leading zeros), similar to standard hash-based proof-of-work schemes. Verification of the resulting proof is efficient, while generation incurs a computational cost proportional to $d \cdot s$.

We now illustrate this approach with two examples.

Counters. As discussed previously, in a counter CRDT supporting operations of the form $inc(n)$, a Byzantine node pk may attempt to issue a single update with a large increment. Under the proposed scheme, the cost function enforces

$C(inc(n), pk, polog) = n$, requiring work proportional to the increment size.

This mechanism also mitigates Sybil attacks.² An adversary controlling many identities and issuing k operations of $inc(1)$ must perform the same total amount of work as issuing a single $inc(k)$, regardless of how the increments are distributed across replicas.

Editable Sequences. For editable sequence CRDTs, the cost function may be defined as proportional to the size of the update. For example, $insert(index, text)$ may incur a cost proportional to the length of $text$, while $delete(index, size)$ incurs a cost proportional to $size$.

More elaborate policies are also possible. By inspecting the local $polog$, the cost function may increase the required work for edits targeting regions that have experienced a high volume of prior modifications. In this way, areas of the document that have attracted more attention can be made progressively harder to change, while preserving availability and convergence.

3.1.1 Resource-Bounded Adversary Model. We model Byzantine participants as resource-bounded adversaries whose ability to impact the system is constrained by the amount of computational effort they can expend. Each update issued by a node must be accompanied by a valid PoW whose cost is determined by the target function $C(op, pk, polog)$ and the difficulty parameter d .

An adversary is characterized by a finite computational budget B , representing the total amount of work it can perform over some period of time. This budget may be distributed arbitrarily across identities (taking into account Sybil attacks). Regardless of which strategy the adversary uses, the total number and cumulative impact of updates that the adversary can inject into the system are bounded by B .

²In these examples, we assume a single datatype and CRDT instance. Systems supporting multiple datatypes in a shared PO-log are not considered for now and should be subject to further analysis.

Correct nodes are assumed to verify proofs of work and accept only updates whose proofs satisfy the required difficulty. Verification is efficient and does not depend on the adversary’s budget.

3.1.2 Bounded Impact of Byzantine Operations. We say that a CRDT instance satisfies the *bounded impact* property if, for any execution and any adversary with computational budget B , the cumulative effect of all updates issued by the adversary is bounded by a function of B , independent of the number of identities under its control.

Formally, let U_A be the set of updates issued by an adversary A , and let

$$\sum_{u \in U_A} C(u) \leq B.$$

Then the total semantic impact of adversarial updates on the replicated state is proportional to B . In particular, distributing work across many replicas does not increase the adversary’s impact beyond what its computational budget permits.

This property directly addresses the limitations identified in earlier sections. In the absence of proof-of-work enforcement, an adversary may issue an unbounded number of valid operations or amplify its impact through Sybil identities. Under the proposed scheme, such behavior remains syntactically valid but quantitatively constrained.

Importantly, bounded impact does not prevent Byzantine nodes from issuing semantically harmful operations; rather, it limits the rate and cumulative magnitude of such harm. Correct nodes continue to make progress independently, preserving the availability and convergence guarantees of CRDTs.

3.1.3 Adaptive Difficulty and Fairness. The difficulty parameter d regulates the expected computational cost of issuing updates and plays a central role in balancing fairness and throughput. While a fixed difficulty may be sufficient in static environments, in open systems, the available computational power and update demand may vary significantly over time. To accommodate such variability, the difficulty parameter can be adjusted dynamically in a decentralized and partition-tolerant manner.

Since a PO-log is a partial order rather than a linear sequence, we avoid reasoning about prefixes and instead consider a replica’s *causally closed view* V of the PO-log. A view V contains a set of updates such that, for every update in V , all of its causal predecessors are also in V . Difficulty adjustment is derived solely from information recorded in such views, without relying on synchronized clocks or coordination.

Each accepted update u carries an associated target cost $s_u = C(u)$, which is either included explicitly or deterministically re-computable from the operation and its causal context. To measure progress in the PO-log without relying on wall-clock time, we define the *work time* of a causally

closed view V as

$$\text{WT}(V) = \sum_{u \in V} C(u) = \sum_{u \in V} s_u,$$

which provides a deterministic and monotonic notion of progress that is preserved under merges.

To define difficulty-adjustment epochs in a partial order, we associate each update u with an intrinsic work-time coordinate derived from its causal past. Let $\text{Past}(u)$ denote the set of causal predecessors of u . We define

$$t(u) = \text{WT}(\text{Past}(u))$$

and assign u to the epoch

$$\text{epoch}(u) = \left\lfloor \frac{t(u)}{E} \right\rfloor,$$

for a fixed epoch size E . This assignment is independent of any total order and is preserved under merges, allowing all replicas to deterministically classify updates into epochs based solely on the PO-log structure. Figure 4 illustrates epoch assignment in a sample PO-log.

To adapt difficulty as computational resources and participation evolve, and to maintain a relatively stable temporal epoch duration, each update may additionally include and sign a locally measured time delta δ_u , representing the elapsed real time spent on the issuer’s PoW. These values are not individually trusted; instead, replicas aggregate them across all updates assigned to the same epoch using a robust statistic (e.g., the median), with Byzantine manipulation bounded as discussed in the Security Discussion in the appendix. Let

$$\widehat{\Delta}_e = \text{median}\{\delta_u \mid u \in V \wedge \text{epoch}(u) = e\}$$

be the estimated duration of epoch e in a replica’s view V .

Given a target epoch PoW duration Δ^* , e.g. 200ms, replicas compute the next difficulty as

$$d_{e+1} = d_e \cdot \frac{\Delta^*}{\widehat{\Delta}_e}.$$

If updates are produced too quickly relative to the target, difficulty increases; if progress is slow, difficulty decreases. This mechanism mirrors the spirit of difficulty adjustment in proof-of-work blockchains. Unlike totally ordered proof-of-work blockchains, in which mining nodes engage in a winner-takes-it-all proof-of-work competition, our proposal is much lighter. Only the node issuing an operation has to do the work imposed by the cost function, and thus, there is no wasted work from competing nodes. In addition, the value chosen by the cost function may be low enough to make it acceptable to humans.³

Temporary divergence in difficulty estimates may occur during network partitions, as replicas observe different causally closed views. However, since difficulty is a deterministic

³Rate limiting is also common to limit password retries when wrong passwords are entered.

Figure 4. Epoch assignment in a PO-log with epoch size $E = 10$. Updates are positioned by the cumulative cost of their causal past. Concurrent updates (d) and (e) fall into different epochs because (e) merges both branches ($t = 12$) while (d) sees only one ($t = 9$). Update (e) deletes 3 characters but incurs work = 6 because difficulty doubles in epoch 1 ($d = 2$).

function of the PO-log contents, replicas converge on the same difficulty once communication resumes and views are merged. No global consensus or leader election is required.

Adaptive difficulty contributes to fairness by ensuring that participants with comparable computational resources achieve comparable long-term impact, independent of the number of identities they control. Importantly, tuning d affects only the rate at which updates can be issued, not their validity or semantics. Correct nodes remain free to issue operations at any time, subject only to the computational effort required. As a result, adaptive difficulty preserves availability and convergence while preventing sustained high-rate attacks that could otherwise overwhelm the system.

While the mechanisms described here rely on simple epoch-based heuristics, more sophisticated policies are possible. For example, difficulty adjustment may incorporate alternative aggregators and sliding windows, or even reputation systems based on historical behavior. We explore such behavior-based alternatives in Section 6.

4 Related Work

Recent work has extended CRDTs to Byzantine environments through different approaches. Jacob et al. [12, 13] demonstrate that state-based CRDTs are inherently equivocation-tolerant. Almeida and Shapiro [2] introduce the blocklace, a DAG-based CRDT that detects equivocators through signed hash chains and eventually excludes Byzantine nodes. Kleppmann and Howard [15] define Byzantine Eventual Consistency for applications inherently immune to Sybil attacks. Sanjuán et al. [21] formalize Merkle-CRDTs, which use hash-chained Merkle-DAG structures to provide causal ordering and efficient syncing in decentralized peer-to-peer settings. While their work establishes the cryptographic foundation for content-addressed CRDT operations, it explicitly assumes non-adversarial replicas and does not

address Sybil resistance or rate-limiting of Byzantine operations. Cholvi et al. [6] present Byzantine-tolerant Distributed Grow-only Sets (BDSO), achieving consensus-free eventual consistency through Byzantine Reliable Broadcast with quorum-based validation.

Consensus-free Byzantine tolerance has also been explored through relaxed ordering models. Frey et al. [9] introduce Process-Commutative distributed objects that relax total ordering requirements to FIFO order per process, achieving Strong Eventual Consistency in Byzantine settings using Mazurkiewicz traces. Their work demonstrates that Byzantine transactional systems can operate without consensus when operations exhibit appropriate commutativity properties, providing a theoretical foundation for understanding the minimal ordering requirements of distributed objects.

Proof-of-work, introduced by Dwork and Naor [7] and popularized by Bitcoin [18], provides Sybil resistance by tying impact to computational resources. While primarily used in consensus protocols, PoW's rate-limiting properties have not been applied to bound Byzantine impact in coordination-free CRDTs. Our work bridges this gap by using PoW to *proactively limit* the update rate of any node, Byzantine or otherwise, thereby bounding adversarial impact *proportionally to computational resources* rather than detecting misbehavior after the fact or relying on membership assumptions.

Finally, the idea of using endorsements or reputation to manage access to CRDT objects is related to prior work on CRDTs and access control [1, 20]. For instance, Renaux et al. [20] propose SRDTs (Secure Replicated Data Types), which associate access rights with CRDT operations to enforce security policies at data replicas. Meanwhile, Almeida [1] discusses identity-management challenges in the context of large-scale CRDT-based systems.

Other work has explored the dual direction, namely how CRDTs themselves can be used to implement access-control

primitives [19, 23, 24]. For example, Weber and Bieniusa [23] show that causally consistent replication can achieve convergence of access-control policies without relying on undo operations, while Yanakieva et al. [24] study CRDT-based access-control in the context of distributed storage. Rault et al. [19] propose mechanisms to combine access control with collaborative editing over CRDT-replicated data. Finally, Frey et al. [8] show that certain access-control objects, such as deny-lists, require consensus for synchronization, albeit only among a limited set of participants. Nonetheless, to the best of our knowledge, using endorsements and reputation as Sybil-resilience mechanisms in the context of CRDT-based replication remains unexplored.

5 Security Discussion: Adversarial Timestamp Manipulation

Our adaptive difficulty mechanism may incorporate per-update elapsed-time reports δ_u supplied by issuers. Since Byzantine participants can choose δ_u arbitrarily, a natural concern is whether adversaries can bias difficulty updates by manipulating these values.

Threat. A Byzantine issuer may report extreme values (e.g., very small δ_u to suggest that epochs complete too quickly, or very large δ_u to suggest sluggish progress) in an attempt to drive difficulty d up or down. If successful, this could either reduce liveness (by inflating d) or enable cheap spam bursts (by deflating d).

Mitigations. We propose two design choices that limit the effectiveness of such manipulation.

First, δ_u values are not interpreted individually. Difficulty updates aggregate δ_u over all updates in an epoch using a robust statistic such as the median (or a trimmed mean). This makes the update rule resilient to a bounded number of outliers: a minority of adversarial reports cannot arbitrarily skew $\widehat{\Delta}_e$.

Second, the proof-of-work mechanism itself constrains the adversary’s ability to flood epochs with manipulative timestamp reports. Injecting many misleading δ_u values requires issuing many updates, which incurs proportional work. Thus, even if an adversary attempts to gain impact over $\widehat{\Delta}_e$ by increasing its sample share, it must pay the corresponding computational cost.

Overall, adversarial timestamp manipulation can affect the responsiveness of adaptive difficulty but does not compromise safety, convergence, or the bounded-impact guarantees: operations remain subject to proof-of-work verification, and any attempt to dominate the difficulty signal requires proportional computational expenditure. Future work could explore verifiable timing mechanisms such as PoSW (Proof of Sequential Work) [17] or VDFs (Verifiable Delay Functions) [4] to strengthen difficulty adaptation.

Threat. A Byzantine node may issue causally valid operations anchored in the past to benefit from a lower epoch difficulty.

Mitigations. In the CRDT model, such operations are indistinguishable from those issued by partitioned honest nodes. As a result, preventing backdated low-cost injections requires restricting honest nodes as well. One mitigation direction is to impose an integration cost for branches where the causally closed view is proportionally much smaller than a more complete view to integrate upon.

6 Discussion, Limitations and Alternatives to Proof-of-Work

While proof-of-work provides a mechanism to bound the cumulative impact of Byzantine operations, it does not eliminate semantic attacks entirely. A sufficiently resourced adversary (such as a state actor or well-funded organization) can still mount harmful operations by expending proportional computational effort. The bounded impact property ensures such attacks are quantitatively constrained, but the cost affects different Byzantine agents heterogeneously: well-resourced attackers face lower barriers than individual malicious nodes.

Moreover, proof-of-work imposes computational and energy costs on all participants, including honest nodes. However, unlike competitive proof-of-work systems such as Bitcoin, where many nodes compete to find a single winning hash and all other computational work is wasted, our approach utilizes every proof: each operation’s computational cost contributes directly to the replicated state. The energy footprint is therefore orders of magnitude lower than blockchain mining. Nevertheless, even this reduced cost may be seen as undesirable, motivating exploration of alternative mechanisms.

An alternative direction leverages reputation systems based on historical behavior. Since operations in Byzantine CRDTs are cryptographically signed, and we have the history of operations within the PO-log, it is possible to attribute beneficial contributions to specific nodes. Consider two application scenarios. In a distributed sensing network monitoring environmental conditions, nodes consistently reporting values within statistically expected bounds could accumulate reputation, which they could later spend on higher-impact operations such as flagging aberrant readings or disputing reports from other nodes. Similarly, in a collaborative editing system, nodes whose edits are not reverted over the last several epochs could earn reputation spendable on reverting others’ edits or making larger modifications. Such reputation-based permission systems could reduce proof-of-work requirements for established cooperative participants and constitute barriers for new and potentially untrusted nodes. Another, somewhat symmetrical approach could rely

on nodes endorsing one another, leveraging cryptographically signed certificates.

Another set of beneficial contributions is protocol-level CRDT operations. Merge operations, where a node creates an update referencing multiple concurrent maximals in the PO-log, directly contribute to system convergence by reducing DAG branching and carry no semantic ambiguity. These operations are (1) *verifiable* from the signed PO-log structure without trusting node claims, (2) *application-agnostic* and thus do not require domain-specific definitions of beneficial behavior. Nodes that consistently perform merge operations could accumulate reputation redeemable for reduced proof-of-work requirements on application-level operations.

Still, designing reputation or endorsement mechanisms for open, partition-tolerant environments introduces three fundamental challenges. First, a larger system necessarily presents a larger attack surface: Byzantine nodes can strategically farm reputation, or endorse one another, through superficially cooperative behavior before exploiting accumulated trust for malicious ends. Second, defining “beneficial behavior” is inherently application-domain specific and might be harder to narrow down formally. Third, embedding permission schemes into CRDT data structures requires new abstractions: the data structure itself would need to encode evolving memberships and reputation scores, potentially exploding complexity on both the state representation and merge semantics.

Hybrid approaches combining both proof-of-work and proof-of-behavior might be the most practical path forward. For example, in a large-scale distributed sensing network where nodes dynamically join and leave, proof-of-work could provide Sybil resistance at the network edge, requiring computational work from new or unknown participants, while established nodes with positive behavioral history operate under reduced work requirements.

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A Instantiating the Cost Function

We now illustrate how the target cost function $C(op, polog)$ can be instantiated for common CRDTs. In each case, the goal is to ensure that the semantic impact of an operation is proportional to the computational effort required to issue it, while preserving the original CRDT semantics.

Counters. For a counter CRDT supporting operations of the form `inc(n)`, a natural choice is

$$C(\text{inc}(n), polog) = n.$$

This enforces a linear relationship between the magnitude of the increment and the required PoW. As a result, issuing a large increment incurs the same total cost as issuing many smaller increments whose sum is equal, regardless of whether these increments are distributed across multiple identities.

Sets. For set CRDTs supporting `add(x)` and `remove(x)` operations, a simple instantiation is a constant cost per element:

$$C(\text{add}(x), polog) = 1, \quad C(\text{remove}(x), polog) = 1.$$

This ensures that adding or removing many elements requires proportional effort. More refined policies are possible; for example, removing elements that have been stable for a long time or that were added by many distinct replicas may incur a higher cost, reflecting their increased semantic weight.

Registers. For register CRDTs that support `write(v)` operations, the cost may depend on the size of the written value:

$$C(\text{write}(v), polog) = |v|,$$

where $|v|$ denotes the size of the value in bytes. This discourages adversarial overwriting with large payloads while allowing small updates at low cost.

Editable Sequences. For sequence CRDTs supporting operations such as `insert(i, text)` and `delete(i, k)`, a natural choice is

$$C(\text{insert}(i, \text{text}), polog) = |\text{text}|,$$

$$C(\text{delete}(i, k), polog) = k.$$

This ensures that the cost of an edit is proportional to the number of elements affected. More elaborate instantiations may incorporate contextual information from *polog*, such as increasing the cost of edits in regions that have experienced frequent prior modifications. Such policies allow heavily contested areas of a document to become progressively harder to change, without sacrificing availability or convergence.

Discussion. These examples illustrate that the cost function T can be tailored to the semantics of each data type, while remaining locally computable and deterministic. Importantly, T does not alter the meaning of CRDT operations or their merge behavior; it merely constrains the rate and cumulative impact of updates that any participant can introduce into the system.